

Genetic Analysis of Lady's Slippers

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Abstract

Showy lady's slippers orchids (*Cypripedium reginae*) are critically endangered in New Hampshire, existing in less than 5 places in the wild. The intent of this experiment was to investigate the genetic diversity of the flowers in the wild, as a lack of genetic diversity can be a significant contribution factor for rate of extinction. This is because genetic diversity allows at least some individuals from a population to survive any sort of external threat such as disease or a change in the environment. To achieve our goal, we performed PCR on DNA samples extracted from plants in the Crossroads Academy's artificial fen, in two separate experiments. These plants were grown in the NHAS Lab from seeds collected from the Eshqua Bog in Vermont. We utilized PCR primers that had been previously used to target variable microsatellite regions on another species of *Cypripedium*. Our experiments identified primers that could be used for our *C. reginae* samples and yielded PCR products that were submitted for DNA sequencing. This produced results for the very short microsatellite segments of DNA. The obtained sequences were analyzed for quality and aligned to determine the amount of difference between individuals. We arrived at the conclusion that, based on this region of DNA, the plants within the Crossroads fen were not genetically different from one another.

Introduction

Cypripedium reginae, more commonly known as the showy lady's slipper, are terrestrial orchids which grow in the upper mid-west and eastern parts of the United States. Within New Hampshire, this plant species is critically endangered. This brings about the question, "are showy lady's slippers' present populations expected to survive and grow?"

When a species is on the brink of extinction, there are two questions that scientists ask to predict their survival: 1) Is the species losing its habitat and 2) what is the variation within the surviving populations? Genetic variation is a measure of the differences in the DNA of different individuals of a species in given populations. A high genetic variation means that the difference between any two lady's slippers' DNA within a given population is large. This indicates that there are enough genetic mutations for at least some of the mutations to be preferred in potentially changing environmental conditions, and the plants with these characteristics would survive.

In the case of showy lady's slippers, genetic variation depends to some extent on how the plants of a population reproduce. There are two ways that showy lady's slippers reproduce – the first is asexually by underground stems and the second is sexually by flowers producing seeds. Reproduction by underground stems is asexual and provides little genetic variation. This method of reproduction is quicker and less subject to environmental changes than sexual reproduction. Although each seed pod contains around 250,000 seeds, reproducing with seeds is challenging.

Less than one percent of these seeds germinate within the first year and less than one percent of the seeds that germinate make it to the flowering stage, which takes eight to ten years.

To help scientists understand the genetic variation of a population of showy lady's slippers, we decided to test the genetic variation in an artificial fen on the campus of Crossroads Academy in Lyme, NH. This fen is 6 years old and was originally populated by about 15 axenically grown seedling all grown from seeds taken from the Eshqua Bog in VT. The fen had 25 plants as of our testing. We hypothesized that there would be a large amount of genetic variation within the fen itself. This would mean that the showy lady's slipper plants had most likely reproduced sexually. This initial study focused on one variable microsatellite region of the lady's slipper genome using primers that had previously been used on another species of *Cypripedium* (*C. tibeticum*) (Li et al., 2017). Studying these more variable regions can begin to give us a sense of the genetic diversity in a population.

Materials and Methods

A list of our experiments is below. Note that the experiments will be described in great detail in the following section.

Experiment 1:

- Sub experiment 1 – Sample Leaf Tip 8, Sample Root Tip 10
- Sub experiment 2 – Sample Root Tip 9, Sample Root Tip 10
- Buffer Troubleshooting

Experiment 2:

- 14 samples, no sub experiments

Experiment 1: For our first main experiment, we collected 8 leaf tip samples and 2 root tip samples from the Crossroads Academy fen, which is a man-made fen. They were grown in the lab from seeds from the Eshqua Bog in Vermont. We crushed the tissue samples with micropestles and performed DNA extraction using QIAGEN's DNeasy Plant Mini Kit, steps 7 and onwards. Then, we used the NanoDrop machine to calculate the DNA concentration of each sample. The three highest concentrations are as follows:

Sample Name	Concentration (ng/μl)
Sample Leaf Tip 8	5.8
Sample Root Tip 9	5.2
Sample Root Tip 10	5.3

We decided to use the two samples with the highest concentrations – Sample Leaf Tip 8 and Sample Root Tip 10, respectively – for sub experiment 1. We tested 6 primers previously used on another orchid in the same genus, *Cypripedium tibeticum* (Li et al., 2017) – m112, m130, m136, m139, m142, and m233. We also performed the same experiment on sample Root Tip 9 and Root tip 10 with primers m886, m880, m681, and m370. We performed PCR using 25ng DNA plus

OneTaq (NEB) with GC Buffer and GC enhancer. A 10x master mix for each of the DNA samples 8 and 10 are listed below:

Sample Leaf Tip 8 Mix

- 33 µL GC Buffer
- 16.5 µL GC Enhancer
- 3.3 µL dNTPs
- 1.65 µL One Taq
- 68.97 µL H₂O
- 28.38 µL Sample Leaf Tip 8

To perform PCR troubleshooting, we had the following setup, where Sample 1 our sample and Sample 2 is another student’s (St. = Standard):

Sample name and amount	A. Sample 1, 25 ng	B. Sample 2, 50 ng	C. Sample 2, 100 ng
Tube 1	GC Buffer + Enhancer	GC Buffer + Enhancer	GC Buffer + Enhancer
Tube 2	GC Buffer + Water	GC Buffer + Water	GC Buffer + Water
Tube 3	St. Buffer + Water	St. Buffer + Water	St. Buffer + shouWater

Experiment 2: We tested primers m172 and m209. Then, we performed this experiment another time with the m209 primers on 14 new samples, from different plants within the Crossroads Academy fen. These samples were named 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, and 14. Samples that yielded bands during gel electrophoresis were sent for DNA sequencing at Eton Biosciences.

Results

Our original PCR to test various primers on our Root Tip 10, Root Tip 9, and Leaf Tip 8 samples did not produce any bands. To troubleshoot the PCR, we tested three different buffer and enhancer combinations that are possible with the OneTaq that we were using. We also tested increasing DNA amounts in the PCR. The strongest bands were in lanes corresponding to reactions with the standard buffer and no enhancer. Our original PCRs utilized the GC buffer and GC enhancer meant for difficult templates. This combination gave no bands in any condition during our troubleshooting.

Only m209 produced any results in the first experiment – we got bands on CA4, CA5, and CA10. So, we sent these out for sequencing. In experiment 2 with 14 samples, PCR worked on samples 1, 3, 5, 6, 7, 9, and 10. Of the 24 samples amplified using m209 primer set, only 10 worked and could be sent out for sequencing.

Figure 1 (above). A chromatogram from sequencing of sample CA4 with the m209 forward primer. The x axis shows the sequence that has been identified by the computer at the top progressing from the beginning of the PCR product to the end. The peaks below indicate what the computer saw and picked out the bases from. It generally picks out the highest peaks. The

colors indicate different bases. The y axis shows the graph of the bases' fluorescence intensity as the labeled base passed by a detector. The beginning of the sequencing run is typically messy and difficult to interpret so it has been omitted here.

Figure 2 (below). Alignment of our two sequencing results with ten samples total. Colors indicate different bases, whose initials are written in the respective colored box. Dashes indicate

points where the alignment software had to skip a base to continue aligning the sequence. This could be the results of a deletion in the sequence with the dash or an insertion in the other sequence(s). Order: 7, 9, CA10, 1, 6, 5, 3, CA5, CA4, 10.

Here, note that in some places, all but one of the sequences align. In such cases, such as base 93, where most sequences are T but one is C, we can determine if the sequences actually line up by checking for double peaks of both bases in **all** the chromatograms. This means we would check if there are double peaks of T and C for base 93 in each chromatogram. If yes, then the sequences from different plants are actually identical at this position despite a difference in the sequence called at that point, meaning that these plants are identical to one another at that point. If no, then the two sequences are different at that point, which can be very important for determining relationships between individuals using such alignments.

Discussion

We must begin by noting that the first 10 primers that we tested that were previously used on *C. tibeticum* did not work at all with the Showy Lady's Slipper samples. This is part of a continuing effort to find usable primers for genetic analysis of the showy lady's slippers. We decided to use a primer set that had worked for a previous student using samples from another fen. This primer set yielded bands for 10 DNA samples.

Our results were that CA4, CA5, CA10, 1, 3, 5, 6, 7, 9, and 10 have similar sequences. This means that they are genetically similar, thus it is possible they are all closely related. However, we cannot say for sure if any of the plants are identical because none of the sequences match completely.

Within these short segments of the DNA sequences, we see some pairs are might be more closely related to one another than they are to another sample. For example, 1 and 6 may be more closely related to each other than either is to 10.

In conclusion, our results do not agree with our hypothesis. The plants are much more genetically similar to one another than we thought they would be. However, these are only looking at one small region of their DNA sequences. Further work that needs to be done includes

repeating the experiment after forming a more organized way of determining which plant each sample came from – it is possible that 1 and 6 were from adjacent plants and 10 was from somewhere else in the fen completely. Repeating sequencing would also let us to confirm if the double peaks are real heterozygosity and not a messy chromatogram. We would also want to analyze more spots in the genome to get a better sense of the difference between plants.

Bibliography

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